

Big Data and its application in Biomedical Domain

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Abstract

Big data [1,2,3] redefined the analytical space with its features such as Volume, Velocity, Variety, Veracity and Value. Due to advancement in the technology, storing, retrieving of data is becoming easier than in the previous decades. Due to this fact, the volume of data in the form of text, image, sound is increasing at a rapid pace in all the fields including the biomedical field [4, 5]. Patient records in the form of electronic medical records are being stored in the data cloud which includes data in different forms. To analyse the data of such magnitude and variety, traditional analytical tools and methods are not sufficient. The Big Data analytical techniques help to analyse these kinds of data and helps us to arrive at decisions quickly. Managing the privacy, security and government regulations related to patient data remains as a challenge [6] in implementing Big Data analytical tools in biomedical domain. This paper starts with the overview of Big Data architecture and moves on to explaining the tools and technologies used in Big Data and the uses of Big Data in Biomedical Field.

Keywords: Biomedical, clinical, Big Data, Hadoop, MapReduce, Spark, Storm, NoSQL, Machine Learning, Deep Learning